

Experimental Study on Buckling and Progressive Damage of Pre-Delaminated Composite Laminates under Compression

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ABSTRACT

A series of pre-delaminated composite laminates are designed and tested, in order to study the buckling and progressive damage behavior of pre-delaminated composite laminates under compressive loading. Strain measurement, C-scan and moire methods are used in combination in the experiment. The sub-laminate buckling, stress re-distribution and delamination propagation are all captured, and effect of delamination location, delamination size and multiple delaminations on buckling and post-buckling behavior of the laminates is analyzed in detail.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to high ratio of strength/stiffness to weight and good corrosion resistance etc., fiber-reinforced composite materials are being widely used in modern aero-plane structures. As one of the most important issues in the design of composite structures, the performance of compression after impact (CAI) has been extensively studied these years [1-3]. However, due to various mechanical properties relate to the final compressive failure, the mechanical meaning of CAI strength is not clear yet [4].

It's believed that delamination could be the main cause of reduced compressive strength [5, 6], so considerable efforts have been made to improve inter-laminar performance by means of developing toughened resin systems [7, 8] or reinforcing through the thickness. Real impact event on a composite laminate will induce various failure modes, such as fiber breakage, matrix cracking and delamination et al. In order to clearly reveal the relationship between delamination and compressive behavior, delamination is usually separated out as a single variable to study. Most of the early works focused on the buckling behavior of sub-laminate with one or more artificial delaminations [5], H. Suemasu et al [4, 9-11] did a lot of work in this field, effect of multiple delaminations on the compressive buckling and post-buckling behavior of composite laminates was investigated using Rayleigh-Ritz method together with experimental observations. L. Gui et al [12] studied the local buckling of a composite laminate with an embedded elliptical delamination, and the variables such as delamination size, delamination angle and stacking sequence were analyzed.

However, previous experimental observations mostly focus on the buckling load and post-buckling behavior, where the progressive damage is less studies, especially the stress redistribution and delamination propagation during the post-buckling process. On the basis of the previous research, this paper in more detail studies the buckling and progressive damage of pre-delaminated laminates, and strain measurement, C-scan and moire methods are used in combination. The effect of delamination location, delamination size and multiple delaminations on buckling and post-buckling behavior of the laminates is analyzed in detail.

2 SPECIMEN AND MATERIAL

In a composite laminate containing damage caused by low velocity impact, intra-laminar transverse cracks can bridge wedge shaped delaminations between adjacent plies into multiple sub-laminates, which can become unstable under compression loading. For example in Fig. 1[4], for an isotropic laminates which is one of the most used stacking sequence, interconnected delaminations spiraling toward the center with four times the ply thickness as a cycle, so the double spiral damage model (DSD) representing real impact damage can be simplified as multiple circular delaminations (MCD),

all of which have the similar buckling, local post-buckling and global post-buckling behavior [4]. Under this assumption, in this paper a series of laminates with different delamination sizes and locations through the thickness are designed and manufactured, as seen in Table 1. ASTM standard [13] recommended that the damage size be limited to half the unsupported specimen width, so take ϕ 40mm pre-delamination as the maximum imperfection size. The groups of CJ2 and CJ3 intend to investigate the effect of delamination location on the compressive behavior, whose delaminations are located at 1/8 and 1/4 thickness of the laminate respectively. CJ5 investigates the effect of delamination size, and CJ6 and CJ7 studies the buckling and progressive damage behavior of multiple delaminated laminates. The stacking sequence of the laminates are all $[45/0/-45-90]_{4s}$, with the nominal thickness of 4mm and overall dimension of 150mm \times 100mm.

Fig. 1 Similarity of the impact-induced delamination to circular delamination [4]

Table 1 Experimental matrix of the pre-delaminated composite laminates

Specimen	Stacking Sequence	Specimen Dimension	Imperfection
CJ2-1~3	$[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$	150 \times 100	ϕ 40 delamination at 1/8 thickness
CJ3-1~3	$[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$	150 \times 100	ϕ 40 delamination at 1/4 thickness
CJ5-1~3	$[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$	150 \times 100	ϕ 30 delamination at 1/4 thickness
CJ6-1~3	$[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$	150 \times 100	ϕ 40 delamination at 1/8 and 1/4 thickness
CJ7-1~3	$[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$	150 \times 100	ϕ 40 delamination at 1/8, 1/4 and 7/8 thickness

The material used in the test is CCF300/5228A. CCF300 is a kind of carbon fiber manufactured by Guangwei Group of China, which has equivalent property as T300 carbon fiber made by Toray Company, and 5228A is a toughened epoxy resin, which is manufactured by Beijing Aeronautic Material Academe of AVIC (Aviation Industry Corporation of China). The artificial delamination was introduced by a non-adhesive film at the prescribed location. There are 3 specimens of each group, and all the test specimens were manufactured in autoclaves at Beijing Aeronautic Material Academe of AVIC. After that C-scan method was used to determine the location of the delaminated circles in the cured plates, which was set as the center to cut the plates into standard dimensions.

3 TEST METHODS

Strain measurement, C scan and moire methods were used in combination in the test, corresponding to the 3 specimens of each group. For the first specimen, strain gages were attached to external surfaces of the laminate, in order to monitor the buckling, delamination propagation and stress distribution during compressive loading. The scheme of strain gages arrangement is depicted in Fig. 2. Take group CJ2 as an example, there are 13 strain gages at each surface of the laminate, the number with capital letters represents the strain gage at the top surface (near the artificial delamination), while the number with small letters is at the bottom surface. FL and FR are far from the delamination area, intending to investigate the global stress redistribution caused by sub-laminate buckling and post-

buckling. M is at the center of the delaminated area, and L15, R15, U15 and D15 are located at four directions relative to M inside the delaminated area, with the distance of 5mm to the delamination edge. The strain gages inside the delamination area are used to monitor the sub-laminate buckling cause by embedded delamination. Since delamination propagates more evidently along the horizontal direction (perpendicular to the loading direction), there are 2 strain gages at the left (L25, L35) and right (R25, R35) side of M respectively, with the interval of 10mm. Similarly one strain gage is at the up and down side of M respectively, that is U25 and D25. These strain gages outside the pre-delamination are intended to monitor the delamination propagation as well as the post-buckling behavior of the laminate.

Fig. 2 Scheme of strain gages arrangement

The compressive loading was applied by a 25T INSTRON electronic universal testing machine, using the standard ASTM CAI fixture as shown in Fig. 3. Metal blocks were put on the top and bottom surfaces of the fixture to assure that the compressive load uniformly applied to the specimen. Before the formal test a 5kN preload was applied to eliminate the fixture clearance, and both the pre-test as well as the formal test were carried out at a constant cross-head speed of 1mm/min while load and displacement were measured automatically by the computer. Strains were measured by the YE2539 static strain indicator produced by Jiangsu Lianneng Corporation, with the sampling interval of 2s. During compressive loading the sounds and other phenomena were also recorded until the final failure of the specimen.

Fig. 3 Compression test fixture and strain monitoring equipment

Having determined the sub-laminate buckling load and ultimate strength, the second specimen of each group was stepwise loaded to percentages of ultimate strength in order to investigate the delamination propagation by C scan method. When the compressive stress reached predetermined load level or obvious sound occurred, the specimen was unloaded and examined by the C scan apparatus as

seen in Fig. 4. This process was repeated to study the post-buckling behavior and progressive damage of the laminate, until final failure of the specimen.

Fig. 4 C scan apparatus used to monitor the delamination propagation

For the third specimen moire method was used, which is a kind of optical measurement method being widely used in scientific research and engineering applications. Moire method has the advantages of real time display and whole field measurement, which can independently evaluate the displacement field and strain field without any disturbance to the tested subject. The basic principle of moire method is using the relative displacement of two gratings to form specific interference fringes. When testing the displacement field, one grating is attached on the tested subject called specimen grating, and the other keeps still called reference grating. During the test the deformed specimen grating and the still reference grating interact to form the interference fringes, whose morphology and order will reflect the whole filed deformation. In this paper the shadow moire method was used, where the specimen grating is not a single grating, but the shadow projected to the specimen by the reference grating under the light. The optical path of shadow moire method is depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Depiction of the optical path of the shadow moire method

A magnetic bearing was designed to apply the moire method to this compression test, as shown in Fig. 6. The bearing was fixed in front of the CAI fixture, with a toughened glass attached by the reference grating, which was made by a high light transmission film with the grating pitch of 0.8mm. The surface of the specimen was painted by matted paint to facilitate observation. Parallel light was projected at a 45-degree angle below the specimen, and a CCD camera was placed perpendicular to the specimen surface to observe the interference strips, also seen in Fig. 6. The moire test as well as the stepwise loaded C scan test were conducted on a 20T WDW-200E electronic universal testing machine made in Jinan of China, and the loading process was the same as strain monitoring test.

Fig. 6 Apparatus used for the measurement by moire method

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental results of the pre-delaminated composite laminates are shown in Table 2, including sub-laminate buckling stresses, ultimate strengths and failure strains, all of which are the average of the three specimens. Failure strains were calculated by dividing the ultimate strengths by modulus of the laminates, and the modulus was derived using the strain values measured by FL (fl) and FR (fr). It can be seen that the delamination size and location have significant effect on the buckling behavior and ultimate strength of the laminate. The detailed experimental results of stress redistribution and damage propagation are described in the following, summarized in Fig. 7 ~ Fig. 11.

Table 2 Experimental results of the pre-delaminated composite laminates

Specimen	Imperfection	Sub-laminate Buckling Stress (MPa)	Ultimate Strength (MPa)	Failure Strain (e^{-6})
CJ2-1~3	$\phi 40$ at 1/8 thickness	156.7	326.6	7267
CJ3-1~3	$\phi 40$ at 1/4 thickness	263.3	312.3	6794
CJ5-1~3	$\phi 30$ at 1/4 thickness	—	367.5	8293
CJ6-1~3	$\phi 40$ at 1/8 and 1/4 thickness	131.7	281.4	6269
CJ7-1~3	$\phi 40$ at 1/8, 1/4 and 7/8 thickness	121.7	280.2	6237

The strain monitoring, C scan and moire observations of CJ2 group are shown in Fig. 7. There are totally 26 strain gages in the specimen, and results are divided into 5 graphs at the upper right of the figure. In the initial stage of loading the 4 strain gages far from the delaminated area (FL, FR, fl and fr) have nearly the same strain values, which indicates good alignment of the specimen. The strain values near the delaminated area have slightly deviation between the top and bottom surfaces, and this may be caused by the weak simply supported constraint in the left and right edges. However the deviation is not significant and doesn't have important influence to the test result, which can be demonstrated in the moire observation. C scan results also show that the delamination doesn't propagate until sub-laminate buckling occurs. The delaminated sub-laminate buckled at about 160MPa compressive stress, and all of the strain values have a sudden jump, with different directions for the top surface (near the artificial delamination) and the bottom surface. For the strain gages far from the delaminated area, FR and FL have smaller compressive strains compared with fr and fl, showing that the side with sub-laminate buckling unloads to a certain extent, while the other side bears a higher proportion of load. When sub-laminate buckling appears some strain gages suddenly fail at the top surface in the bucked

area, as a result of the large buckling deformation shown in the moire observation.

Fig. 7 Strain monitoring, C scan and moire observations of CJ2 group

The strain gages near the artificial delamination intend to monitor the sub-laminate buckling and delamination propagation. Combined with the C scan results, it can be seen that delamination propagation simultaneously happened with sub-laminate buckling, while delamination propagated instantaneous with a large length along the horizontal direction than the vertical direction. Regarding the strain gages in the horizontal direction (colored yellow and blue in the figure), the nearer to the center of the delaminated area, the more intensely strain values jump during sub-laminate buckling, with L15 and L25 failed due to large deformation. L35 and l35 are relatively far from the delamination center and have smaller changes, showing that the delamination propagated about 10mm along the horizontal direction when sub-laminate buckling occurred. The compressive strain values of L35 increased nonlinearly after sub-laminate buckling, which means there was a stress concentration by the side of the delaminated sub-laminate. It's worth noting that the compressive strain values of l15 and l25 also decreased, with a more extent nearer to the delamination center, indicating the thicker sub-laminate (7/8 thickness) also deform to the reverse direction. The strain gages at the right side are symmetric with the left side, and have the same changing trend.

The lower two graphs are showing the strain values in the vertical direction near the artificial delamination. U15, M and D15 are in the delaminated area, which behaved more intensely strain values jump than the horizontal direction, so the sub-laminate unloaded more seriously in the vertical direction. Strain values at the back side (u15, m and d15) also decreased caused by the thicker sub-laminate deformation mentioned above. U25 and D25 are outside the pre-delaminated area, showing less strain values jump during sub-laminate buckling. Combined with the C scan results it can be seen that the delamination propagated little along the vertical direction. The u25 and d25 showed a little increase by the compressive strain value during sub-laminate buckling, which also indicates the stress concentration around the buckled sub-laminate.

After local buckling the out-of-plane displacement of the sub-laminate increased continually, which can be proved in the moire observation. The unbuckled side of the laminate carried a growing proportion of load, seen in the nonlinear variation of the strain values. When close to the final failure of the laminate, all of the strain values once again have a sudden jump, and this may be caused by the unstable delamination propagation along the horizontal direction. Soon afterward the laminates failed catastrophically. The stress-displacement curves and failure morphologies are shown in Fig. 12. It can be seen that the buckled sub-laminate didn't fracture, while fiber failure occurred at the left and right edges of the laminate. Combined with strain monitoring and C scan results, it can be concluded that the final failure mode of the delaminated laminates was fiber compressive breakage, which was caused by stress concentration due to sub-laminate buckling.

The compressive failure process of CJ3 group was similar to CJ2, as shown in Fig. 8. Since delamination was placed at 1/4 thickness, the corresponding buckling stress was larger than CJ2, with more intensively strain values jump. According to the strain gages of L35 and R35 which also failed in sub-laminate buckling, it can be seen that the delamination suddenly propagated to a length of more than 15mm in the horizontal direction. The thicker sub-laminate also buckled but with a smaller range, and the strain values of l35 and r25 increased due to stress concentration. The ultimate strength of CJ3

is smaller than CJ2, and the bulked sub-laminate also failed in fiber breakage.

Fig. 8 Strain monitoring, C scan and moire observations of CJ3 group

With a smaller delaminated area in the thickness of 1/4, CJ5 didn't behave sub-laminate buckling until final failure, as shown in Fig. 9. The strain values far from the delaminated area coincided well, while the others separated at about 150MPa by the top and bottom surface. From the C scan and moire observations it can be demonstrated that the laminate failed in global buckling without delamination propagation before final failure. However the delamination propagated along with the final failure of the laminate. The ultimate strength of CJ5 is also the highest of the 5 groups.

Fig. 9 Strain monitoring, C scan and moire observations of CJ5 group

There are two delaminations in the CJ6 group, located at 1/8 and 1/4 thickness of the laminate respectively. The strain values varied similarly as CJ2 group as seen in Fig. 10, and the problem which needs to pay close attention is the propagation behavior of the two delaminations. C scan results show that when sub-laminate occurred, the two delaminations all propagated along the horizontal direction, and the delaminated area after final failure was smaller than CJ2 and CJ3. Referring to the stress-displacement curve it can be seen that the delamination propagated progressively until final failure. The sub-laminate buckling stress as well as the ultimate strength of CJ6 is smaller than CJ2 and CJ3, indicating that multiple delaminations could further lower the bearing capacity of the sub-laminate. When there is an extra artificial delamination at 7/8 thickness (CJ7 group), the sub-laminate buckling stress and ultimate strength didn't change significantly. At every load level C scan was conducted twice, where the top surface and the bottom surface was upward respectively. The latter intends to study the propagation behavior at 7/8 thickness during compressive loading. From the cross-section scanning results, it can be seen that the artificial delamination at 7/8 thickness didn't propagate until final failure of the laminate, which demonstrated that the extra delamination has little effect on the compressive behavior compared with CJ6 group.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the paper a series of pre-delaminated laminates are designed and tested, in order to quantitatively study the effect of delamination on buckling and progressive damage behavior. Strain monitoring, C scan and moire methods are used in combination. It can be concluded that the delamination size and location greatly influence the buckling stress and compressive strength of the laminates, as seen in Table 2. Delamination propagation simultaneously happens with sub-laminate buckling, and the

delamination mainly propagates along the horizontal direction. Sub-laminate buckling and delamination propagation induce stress redistribution along the thickness of the laminate, globally the side without delamination bears a higher proportion of load. Sub-laminate buckling also includes stress concentration close to the buckled area, and the final failure mechanism of the laminate is fiber compressive fracture. When there are two delaminations in 1/8 and 1/4 thickness, they all propagate with a similar length under compressive load. The delamination at 7/8 thickness doesn't propagate, which has little effect on the compressive behavior of the laminate.

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